

EFFECTIVENESS OF READING ALOUD STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING READING HABITS

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Abstract:

Read aloud strategy is essential; it determines the success of the future. The focus of present study was on read-aloud strategy and other reading strategies. Mainly the purpose of this study was to check the effectiveness of different reading strategies, which could be helpful at elementary level. The present study was based on reading habits of students at elementary level. The study was conducted in a Govt. Girls Elementary School Fateh Wala, Multan. Data was collected from grade 8 students. Data was collected with the help of questionnaire; pretest, posttest was also used to collect data from students. A sample size of 25 students was taken in which ten were female, and 15 male students had participated. Ten teachers also participated in this research work in which 5 were male teachers and five were female. A comparative analysis was conducted for students reading habits with reading-aloud and silent reading strategy.

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Atlas ti 8 updated version was used for literature review. Results include the finding that read aloud strategy is better than silent reading and other reading strategies at elementary level.

Keywords: reading habits, reading aloud strategies, silent reading strategies, elementary level

1. Introduction

Read aloud strategy helps build up the knowledge and skills for future success. Reading aloud strategy enables students to understand the high-level languages and in understanding the text written in other languages like reading the stories and any written text. Read aloud approach is also helpful in improving the vocabulary, grammar, and any written information. It enables children to write down text quickly and enhance the reading understanding.

Figure 1: Year wise systematic literature review output of ATLAS ti 8

Figure 1 demonstrate the semantic links for the introduction completed for the research studies conducted from 1985 to 2017. Routman (2003). Read aloud provides a base for comprehension strategies. It provides an assessment for learning Bereiter and Bird (1985). Students prefer to read novels, magazines and storybooks, historic, romantic and entertaining stuff at university level Erdem (2015). Students are being motivated for self-reading to obtain better grades and improve their academic needs

related to reading at primary level. Girls are more avid readers than boys and reading is one of the leisure activities for children (Majid and Tan, 2007). Very few students have good reading habits and spend their time regularly reading English text. EFL students learn English book for their assignments, pleasure and to improve their skills for English language communication (Iftanti, 2012). RAS is predominantly adopted at elementary level (Marchessault and Larwin, 2014). Read aloud strategy enhance the curiosity among the students and improve their representing abilities Harvey (1998). Reading aloud is helpful not only for primary level students but also for elementary and high school levels. It helps out students for poems, short stories and reading any English written text easily. RAS engage students interactively during the process Sanacore (1987). Students understand the importance of reading because it is a gateway to success in education. It's just like a heartbeat in educational institutes and crucial for learning process (Florence et al., 2017).

2. Review of Literature

Figure 2: Atlas ti 8 output for systematic literature review

Figure 2 exhibits research studies from 1985 to 2018 which were reviewed as a systematic literature review in Atlas ti 8. Detailed explanation is given below.

Kucukoglu (2013) have explained about improving reading skills through the active reading strategies. Yussof et al. (2012) have explained about enhancing the reading comprehension through cognitive strategies. A quasi-experimental method was used, and a sample size of 45 participants was taken for this study. Graphic study with activity-based learning was found significant in improving the comprehension skills of

the students. Findings showed that cognitive comprehension strategies were found helpful. Gambrel (1996) has highlighted developing classroom cultures that foster reading motivation among students. Results showed that books were found an essential source of intrinsic level of reading for students. Intrinsic rewards were found necessary in enhancing reading capabilities. Mckeown and Gentilucci (2007) highlighted about think-aloud strategy. The study was conducted in a middle school for metacognitive development and monitoring comprehension. Findings showed that for reading comprehension different strategies were needed because different approaches were showing mixed results for improving knowledge.

Gooden et al. (2007) pointed out about metacognitive strategies important in enhancing reading skills of students. The study found that for better understandings of words synonyms and antonyms were meaningful. Vocabulary and related words material were found a helpful tool in enhancing the reading comprehension in poor readers. Juel (1988) explained about learning to read and write. Findings showed that children who were found destitute in early grades they would remain poor in all the next classes. The study highlighted that good reader showed writing skills while poor readers showed poor writing skills with poor reading. Wadsworth (2008) explained about using the read-aloud strategy in classrooms. The study pointed out that an increasing trend was responsible for creating a stressful environment for students. The study pointed out that no attention was given over phonics and language rules. Ledger and Merga (2018) have explained children attitudes towards read-aloud strategy at home or school. The study highlighted that read aloud strategy was found helpful in developing independent practice and in self-reading. Most respondents showed a significant attitude towards read-aloud plan in school and in-home. Read aloud strategy helped perceive cognitive benefits because with its students were learning difficult words and their pronunciation. A student's mental and physical activity was found responsible for being a good reader. Marchessault and Larwin (2013) highlighted about structured read-aloud strategy at school level. Findings showed that read aloud strategy was found helpful at school level and it had a significant impact on students' DORA (Diagnostic Online Reading Assessment) test. Read aloud was a cost-free approach for teachers. Read aloud was found helpful especially for traditional contents of middle level, and for passage reading also read aloud was helping student in comprehension development. Fuchs et al. (2013) examined about effects of peer-assisted learning strategies at school level related to reading problems. Findings showed that PALS (Peer Assisted Learning Strategies) were correlated with reading problems.

Qanwal and Karim (2014) had highlighted the correlation between reading strategies instruction and L2 text comprehension. Findings showed a significant relationship between reading strategies and learner's proficiency in comprehension reading. It was found that reading was playing an important role for ESL readers. Reading strategies could improve by direct instruction and was notable for native readers. Awais and Ameen (2013) highlighted the reading preferences of elementary school children in Lahore. Findings showed that English readers prefer to read

instruction material published locally. Many students preferred to read adventure and fiction material. Results showed that local media could play a vital role in developing reading habits. Kucukoglu (2013) explained about improving the reading skills through effective reading strategies. Findings showed that different strategies helped improve the reading habit of students. Fisher et al. (2013) explained about interactive read aloud. The study showed significant results for read-aloud strategy that teachers who had lack of practice; read aloud allow these teachers to read independently and fluently. Caldwell and Leslie (2010) highlighted about thinking aloud in expository text. The study was conducted in a middle school. The study showed highly significant results for thinking aloud strategy, and it was considered that read aloud strategy was very useful for recalling the text. Bereiter and Bird (1985) pointed out the use of thinking aloud in identification and teaching of reading comprehension strategies.

3. Material and Methods

The present study was based on reading habits of students at elementary level. The study was conducted in a Govt. Girls Elementary School Fateh Wala, Multan. Data was collected from grade 8 students. Data was collected with the help of questionnaire; pre-test post-test was also used to collect data from students. A sample size of 25 students was taken in which ten were female, and 15 male students had participated. Ten teachers also participated in this research work in which 5 were male teachers, and five were female. For pre-test and post-test analysis data was taken from the novels "Pride and prejudice" and "A mill on the floss" to check the reading ability of the students for both the strategies of reading. A comparative analysis was conducted for students' reading habits with read-aloud and silent reading strategies.

4. Results & Discussion

In table 1, it can be observed that respondent one has scored 10% marks while response in post-test was 80%. Respondent 2 has scored 40% marks in pre-test, while in post-test results are 100%. Respondent 3 has scored 60% in pre-test, while in post-test 70% marks were obtained. Respondent 4 has scored 20% marks in pre-test while in post-test has scored 100% marks. Respondent 5 has scored 30% marks in pre-test while 100% marks in post-test. Respondent 6 has scored 50% marks in pre-test while 70% marks in post-test. Respondent 7 has scored 30% marks in pre-test while 60% marks in post-test. Respondent 8 has scored 20% marks in pre-test while 90% marks in post-test. Respondent 9 has scored 10% marks in pre-test while 70% marks in post-test. Respondent 10 has scored 30% marks in pre-test while 60% marks in post-test. Respondent 11 has scored 20% marks in pre-test while 80% marks in post-test. Respondent 12 has scored 50% marks in pre-test while 80% marks for post-test. Respondent 13 has scored 50% marks in pre-test while 70% marks in post-test. Respondent 14 has scored 10% marks in pre-test while 90% marks in post-test. A

respondent 15 has scored 20% marks in pre-test while 80% marks in post-test. Respondent 16 has scored 20% marks in pre-test while 80% marks in post-test. Respondent 17 has scored 50% marks in pre-test while 60% marks in post-test. Respondent 18 has scored 50% marks in pre-test while 70% in post-test. Respondent 19 has scored 30% marks in pre-test while 90% marks in post-test. Respondent 20 has scored 50% marks in pre-test while 90% marks in post-test. Respondent 21 has scored 30% marks in pre-test while 80% marks in post-test. Respondent 22 has scored 40% marks in pre-test while 60% marks in post-test. Respondent 23 has scored 20% marks in pre-test while 80% marks in post-test. Respondent 24 has scored 30% marks in pre-test while 100% marks in post-test. Respondent 25 has scored 40% marks in pre-test while 90% marks in post-test.

Table 1: Comparison of pre-test and post-test in percentages

Pre-test results		Post-test results	
Respondents	Obtained Percentage	Respondents	Obtained Percentage
1	10%	1	80%
2	40%	2	100%
3	60%	3	70%
4	20%	4	100%
5	30%	5	100%
6	50%	6	70%
7	30%	7	60%
8	20%	8	90%
9	10%	9	70%
10	30%	10	60%
11	20%	11	80%
12	50%	12	80%
13	50%	13	70%
14	10%	14	90%
15	60%	15	70%
16	20%	16	80%
17	50%	17	60%
18	50%	18	70%
19	30%	19	90%
20	50%	20	90%
21	30%	21	80%
22	40%	22	60%
23	20%	23	80%
24	30%	24	100%
25	40%	25	90%

Tables 2, 3, and 4 are concerned with t-test results. In table 2, pre-test and post-test were compared by using the t-statistics. Results were obtained by using the SPSS software. Results had shown that mean value for pre-test was .50, while for post-test mean value was .70. Table 3 shows that the standard deviation of pre-test was .513 while for post-test it was .470. Standard error mean for pre-test was .115, while for post-test it was .105.

In table 2 paired sample test difference show that mean value difference of pre-test post-test was -.200, for standard deviation it was .616, standard error mean was .138 and $t = 1.453$. Statistical analysis results showed that in reading strategies student's attitude towards read-aloud strategy was positive as compared to silent reading strategy. Students had performed better in read-aloud strategy as compared to silent reading. It was found that students had not only performed better with read-aloud strategy in pre-test post-test but also questionnaire results. Whereas table 4 shows the paired sample correlations which were .218, and for total population of 20 students, the significance was .355.

Table 1: Statistical analysis for pre-test post-test results with paired t-test in SPSS

Paired Samples Test							t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Paired Differences			95% Confidence Interval of the Difference					
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper				
Pair 1	Pretest - Posttest	-.200	.616	.138	-.488	.088	-1.453	19	.163

Table 2: Statistical analysis for pre-test post-test results with paired t-test in SPSS

Paired Samples Statistics					
		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	Pretest	.50	20	.513	.115
	Posttest	.70	20	.470	.105

Table 3: Paired sample correlations

Paired Samples Correlations				
		N	Correlation	Sig.
Pair 1	Pretest & Posttest	20	.218	.355

A. Students Questionnaire response

The response of students in provided questionnaire was different.

Table 4: Summarizing is helpful reading aloud strategy

Q1: Summarizing is a valuable read-aloud strategy?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	12	48.0	48.0	48.0
	A	9	36.0	36.0	84.0
	N	1	4.0	4.0	88.0
	DA	3	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Student's response for Q.1 **Summarizing is helpful read-aloud strategy** was mixed. 48% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement, 36% of respondents agreed, 4% of respondents were neutral while 12% of respondents disagreed.

Table 5: Read aloud strategy is helpful in translation

Q2: Read aloud approach is useful to translation					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	10	40.0	40.0	40.0
	A	9	36.0	36.0	76.0
	N	5	20.0	20.0	96.0
	DA	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Student's response for Q.2 **Read aloud strategy is helpful in translation** was mixed. 40% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement, 36% of respondents agreed, 20% of respondents were neutral, 4% of respondents disagreed for the question.

Table 6: If teachers read aloud, I can easily understand

Q3: If teachers read aloud, I can easily understand					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	12	48.0	48.0	48.0
	A	9	36.0	36.0	84.0
	N	3	12.0	12.0	96.0
	DA	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Student's response for Q.3, if teachers read aloud, I can easily understand was 48% of respondents strongly agreed, 36% of respondents agreed, 12% of respondents were neutral, while 1% of respondents disagreed.

Table 7: Do you think visualization enhance confidence while reading aloud

Q4: Do you think visualization increase confidence while reading aloud					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	16	64.0	64.0	64.0
	A	3	12.0	12.0	76.0
	N	6	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Student's response for Q.4, Do you think visualization enhance confidence while reading aloud, 64% of respondents strongly agreed, 12% of respondents agreed, while 24% of respondents were neutral.

Table 8: I enjoy with read-aloud strategy

Q5: I enjoy with read-aloud strategy					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	12	48.0	48.0	48.0
	A	10	40.0	40.0	88.0
	N	3	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Student's response for Q.5, **I enjoy with read-aloud strategy**, 48% of respondents strongly agreed, 40% of respondents agreed, while 12% of respondents were neutral.

Table 9: Read aloud is better than silent reading strategy

Q6: Read aloud is better than silent reading strategy for developing reading habits					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	11	44.0	44.0	44.0
	A	7	28.0	28.0	72.0
	N	5	20.0	20.0	92.0
	DA	2	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Students' response for Q.6, **Read-aloud is better than silent reading strategy**, 44% of respondents strongly agreed, 28% of respondents agreed, 20% of respondents were neutral while 8% of respondents disagreed.

Table 10: Questioning is helpful in reading aloud habits

Q7: Questioning is helpful in reading aloud habits					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	15	60.0	60.0	60.0
	A	8	32.0	32.0	92.0
	N	2	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Students response for Q.7, **Questioning helps read aloud?** 60% of respondents strongly agreed, 32% of respondents agreed, while 8% of respondents were neutral.

Table 11: Read aloud is helpful in enhancing confidence of reading habits

Q8: Read aloud is helpful in enhancing confidence of reading habits					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	14	56.0	56.0	56.0
	A	7	28.0	28.0	84.0
	N	4	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Students' response for Q 8, **Read-aloud helps enhance confidence of reading habits**, 56% of respondents strongly agreed, 28% of respondents agreed, while 16% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 12: Reading is important in the learning process

Q9: Reading is important in the learning process					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	14	56.0	56.0	56.0
	A	8	32.0	32.0	88.0
	N	3	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Student's response for Q. 9, **Reading is important in the learning process**, 56% of respondents strongly agreed, 32% of respondents agreed, while 12% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 13: Do you feel confident in reading any text aloud?

Q10: Do you feel confident with reading any text aloud?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	9	36.0	36.0	36.0
	A	11	44.0	44.0	80.0
	N	4	16.0	16.0	96.0
	DA	1	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	25	100.0	100.0	

Students response for the Q.10, **Do you feel confident with reading any text aloud?** 36% of respondents strongly agreed, 44% of respondents agreed, 16% of respondents were neutral, while 4% of respondents disagreed for the statements.

B. Teacher's Questionnaire response

Table 14: Do you prefer to read aloud strategies over silent reading strategies for developing your reading habits?

Q1: Do you prefer to read aloud strategies over silent reading strategies for developing your reading habits?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	6	60.0	60.0	60.0
	A	3	30.0	30.0	90.0
	N	1	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers response for Q.1, **Do you prefer to read aloud strategy?** 60% of respondents strongly agreed, 30% of respondents agreed, while 10% of respondents were neutral for the statements.

Table 15: Do you think the read-aloud strategies are helpful for students in developing their reading habits at this elementary level?

Q2: Do you think the read-aloud strategies are helpful for students in developing their reading habits at this elementary level?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	5	50.0	50.0	50.0
	A	5	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers response for the Q. 2, **Do you think read-aloud strategy is helpful for students**, 50% of respondents strongly agreed while 50% of respondents agreed for the statements.

Table 16: Read aloud is helpful in adherence with background

Q3: Read aloud is helpful in adherence with background					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	4	40.0	40.0	40.0
	A	5	50.0	50.0	90.0
	N	1	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers' response for Q.3, **Read-aloud is helpful in adherence with background**, 40% of respondents strongly agreed, 50% of respondents agreed, while 1% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 17: Read aloud enables students for open ended questions

Q4: Read aloud enables students for open ended questions					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	4	40.0	40.0	40.0
	A	5	50.0	50.0	90.0
	N	1	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers response for Q.4, **Read aloud enables students for open-ended questions**, 40% of respondents strongly agreed, 50% of respondents agreed, while 10% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 18: Read aloud is a helpful strategy for story reading habits

Q5: Read aloud is helpful strategy for story reading habits					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	2	20.0	20.0	20.0
	A	7	70.0	70.0	90.0
	N	1	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers response for the Q.5, **Read-aloud is helpful strategy for story reading**, 20% of respondents strongly agreed, 70% of respondents agreed, 10% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 19: I prefer recapitulation before delivering my lecture

Q6: I prefer recapitulation before delivering my lecture					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	4	40.0	40.0	40.0
	A	5	50.0	50.0	90.0
	N	1	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teacher's response for Q.6, **I prefer recapitulation before delivering my lecture**, 40% of respondents strongly agreed, 50% of respondents agreed, while 10% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 20: Read aloud helping in building confidence in poor readers

Q7: Read aloud helping in building confidence in poor readers					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	6	60.0	60.0	60.0
	A	4	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teacher's response for Q.7, **Read aloud helping in building confidence in poor readers**, 60% of respondents strongly agreed, 40% of respondents agreed for the statement.

Table 21: Read aloud is comparatively better than silent reading

Q8: Read aloud is relatively better than silent reading					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	5	50.0	50.0	50.0
	A	2	20.0	20.0	70.0
	N	3	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers' response for Q.8, **Read-aloud is relatively better than silent reading**, 50% of respondents strongly agreed, 20% of respondents agreed, while 30% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 22: Is inferring strategy help read aloud?

Q9: Is inferring strategy help read aloud?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	2	20.0	20.0	20.0
	A	6	60.0	60.0	80.0
	N	2	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teacher's response for Q.9, **Is inferring strategy help read aloud**, 20% of respondents strongly agreed, 60% of respondents agreed, while 20% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

Table 23: Read aloud is better for the second language

Q10: Read aloud is better for the second language					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SA	4	40.0	40.0	40.0
	A	3	30.0	30.0	70.0
	N	3	30.0	30.0	100.0
	Total	10	100.0	100.0	

Teachers response for Q.10, **Read-aloud is better for second language**, 40% of respondents strongly agreed, 30% of respondents agreed, while 30% of respondents were neutral for the statement.

From the above results, it could be concluded that different students prefer different reading strategies. But overall results showed that summarizing was helpful for read-aloud strategy. Most of the students found read-aloud approach was helpful for translation method. Most students had shown positive responses for read-aloud plan of teachers. They understand whatever teachers deliver to them with read-aloud strategy. Students showed positive results for visualization that read aloud approach enhance with display. Students take read-aloud strategies helpful and enjoy by read-aloud text as compared to silent reading. Students showed a fuller difference in results for read-aloud strategy and other reading strategies. The questioning was also helpful for read-aloud strategy. The questioning was also beneficial for enhancing confidence among students.

Read aloud strategies were not only useful in building trust but also playing role for learning process. It was developing a good reading habit among students by which not only students were being benefitted, but it was also helpful for their learning. The teachers' response was also in favor of read-aloud strategy as compared to any other reading habit. They had also shown positive results for read-aloud strategies, which they preferred in their lectures. They had demonstrated significant differences for read-aloud strategies that they help adhere to background and it is very helpful in developing coherence with background knowledge. They showed results for read-aloud strategy that it is useful for open-ended questions also for storytelling. Read aloud is important in recapitulation and in building confidence among poor readers. It is an inferring strategy and better than other reading strategies for students. To sum up, both the participants either students or teachers recommended reading aloud strategies for developing good reading habits among the students, and both did not favor silent reading strategies for developing reading habits among students at elementary level.

5. Recommendations

Reading has a significant role in the learning process. Its importance could not be neglected. Among all the reading strategies read-aloud strategy is crucial.

Figure 3: Suggestions

Figure 3 reveals Atlas it 8 output on the recommendations of the authors regarding reading aloud strategies role for developing students' reading habits at elementary school level. Read aloud strategy is not only important at elementary level but for all the levels of learning. Pakistan is a country in which national language is Urdu and

majority of people have no understanding of foreign language. English language is getting importance in different areas, yet it is difficult for people to understand it. At school level teachers are teaching English language as a compulsory subject. Students who are from rural areas have poor understanding of English language. Teachers should opt read-aloud strategy for those students who are deficient in English language. Read aloud strategy is vital for also those students who are not confident. Teachers should develop reading aloud habit among new school-going children. In this way they must be able to overcome their hesitation for English language, and their pronunciation will also improve by reading aloud a text. Students were found distracted by spellings, pronunciation, and reading English language when not using reading aloud strategies. Thus, read-aloud strategy is beneficial because it avoids distraction of students from learning, so it is needed that teachers should focus on read-aloud strategy. By developing the habit of reading aloud teachers can overcome their student's hesitation for speaking publicly. For those students who are native developing read aloud habits could be helpful because it will not demotivate them in learning international language and they will feel comfortable. In educational institute read-aloud strategy must be encouraged because it keeps students active and helps them for memorization. However, further research is recommended on the issue whether reading aloud can better develop students' reading habits than other competitive strategies.

6. Conclusion

Read aloud strategy is vital for learning process because it helps build confidence among students; overcome their hesitation for reading English language. It supports native readers and encourages them to overcome their reluctance for English. It not only improves the internal listening skills of readers but also enhances the spelling awareness among students. It is a source of developing student's interest in reading English and in picking up their own mistakes by reading aloud a text. Comparing with other reading strategies, this strategy support only high proficiency readers while RA helps not only competent readers but also low proficiency readers as well. It is one vital strategy that develops students' reading habit nicely.

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